

D1.2 Quality and Risk Management Plan

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Abbreviations

DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
NCC	National Capacity Centre(s)
QRMP	Quality and Risk Management Plan
RMP	Risk Mitigation Plan
STB	Services and Technology Board
WP	Work Package(s)
WPLM	Work Package Leaders' Meeting

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Executive Summary

The aim of the Quality and Risk Management Plan is to design and implement management and quality assurance processes that ensure the effective use of project resources and the timely delivery of high-quality outputs. The Plan defines the tools, methodologies, and measures to track and assess progress against the project's predefined objectives. Additionally, the Plan presents a framework for the proactive identification, analysis, and monitoring of potential risks, as well as workflows to define contingency plans to mitigate their impact.

These iterative processes outlined in the document ensure accountability, robust governance and informed decision-making in alignment with the project's overall goals and quality standards.

1. Introduction

The Quality and Risk Management Plan (QRMP) defines the framework, procedures, and responsibilities established to ensure the high-quality implementation of AEGIS-OA and the effective identification, assessment, and mitigation of risks throughout its lifecycle. As a deliverable of T1.1 (Project Management), the Plan outlines the necessary resources, documentation, and tools for day-to-day management; it also identifies measures to support smooth progress and timely delivery of results in alignment with the project's objectives, timelines, and key performance indicators.

The QRMP covers both administrative and technical aspects, including the production of deliverables, achievement of milestones, data management, and reporting. More specifically, the QRMP aims to:

- Establish a structured approach to quality assurance and quality control across all project activities;
- Define processes for continuous monitoring and evaluation;
- Provide a methodology for identifying and managing risks;
- Ensure transparency, accountability, and consistency in project implementation

The plan is aligned with the project's Grant Agreement and Description of Action (DoA). It complements other project management documents, including the Data Management Plan (DMP; D1.1) and the Dissemination, Outreach and Exploitation Plan (D1.3). The QRMP integrates quality standards and risk mitigation processes into the project decision-making processes, and thus applies to all project partners, Work Packages (WP), and activities described in the DoA.

2. Quality Management

2.1. Methodology

The project implementation framework follows an iterative methodology that integrates quality assurance into its workflows. AEGIS-OA comprises six Work Packages (WPs), structured around two primary activity types:

- **Operational management (WP1):** focuses on the continuous monitoring, administration, and communication required to ensure alignment across ongoing tasks and dissemination of their outputs.
- **Development (WP2-WP6):** focuses on resource development and the eventual integration of resources and services into the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH).

The interaction between WPs is bidirectional, thus allowing continuous monitoring and timely implementation of risk mitigation measures: WP1 feeds into WPs 2-6 by assessing progress, ensuring alignment with the project's core objectives, and coordinating communication and outreach activities. WP 2-6 keep WP1 informed of their progress and results. This reporting mechanism allows WP1 to identify risks and adjust the workplan as needed.

Image 1. WP structure and synergies

The project implementation plan is structured around two main phases and builds on processes and practices previously validated during the initial development of the EDCH.

The first phase focuses on the production of project outputs through a co-creation approach, both internally among consortium partners and externally with relevant stakeholders. This collaborative model enhances the relevance, usability, and impact of project outputs. Quality assurance during this phase is therefore embedded in the collaborative process itself, relying on structured feedback mechanisms, stakeholder engagement, and shared responsibility across partners.

The second phase involves the integration of outputs developed across different work packages into the corresponding EDCH platforms and services, ensuring consistency and interoperability. This structured integration reduces discrepancies and redundancies between components and establishes systematic workflows for ongoing feedback, updates, and refinement. The foreseen milestones and deliverable submission dates will ensure that all anticipated results/input (design phase) and final outputs (implementation phase) are available in a timely manner, in alignment with each WP timeline and the Description of Action. This integration phase may be carried out progressively or at the end of the project, depending on the output type.

Image 2. Stages of implementation

2.2 Project management and coordination

The AEGIS-OA consortium comprises 14 Beneficiary organisations and 10 Associated Partners, representing established National Capacity Centres (NCCs) across Europe. The roles and anticipated involvement of all partners are defined in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, and are operationalised through the project's governance structure.

2.2.1 Governance structure and decision-making

The governance model secures broad representation, transparent decision-making, and efficient coordination across all project activities. It serves as an integrated framework that distributes responsibilities and facilitates the collaboration of the following interconnected bodies:

The **General Assembly** consists of one representative per Beneficiary and Associated Partner and serves as the consortium's decision-making body. It is responsible for:

- Approving strategic decisions and validating any changes to the DoA, budget allocations, and resource distribution;
- Ensuring alignment with project objectives and overall quality standards

The Chair of the General Assembly is elected during the first meeting and serves for the entire project duration. Regular meetings of the General Assembly will be scheduled to monitor progress, address strategic risks, and ensure informed decision-making.

The **Coordinator** acts as the legal and administrative intermediary between the consortium and the Granting Authority and holds overall responsibility for project implementation. The Coordinator is responsible for implementing all the necessary procedures and measures to ensure the overall compliance with the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, by:

- Managing the financial contribution and ensuring proper financial administration;
- Coordinating the preparation of, and submitting all required reports, financial statements, and supporting documentation to the European Commission

- Ensuring effective communication and information sharing among consortium members and with external stakeholders.

The **Executive Committee** acts as the supervisory and operational management body within the project. It oversees the day-to-day execution of the project and is responsible for implementing quality assurance and risk monitoring procedures. It comprises the two Principal Investigators of the project, and two Project Managers, whose responsibilities include:

- Supporting WP Leaders in operational decision-making;
- Reviewing project outputs for consistency, quality, and compliance; collecting, reviewing, and submitting project deliverables in a timely manner;
- Identifying cross-cutting issues, interdependencies, and risks that may affect overall project performance; maintaining and updating the project work plan;

The complementary roles of the Coordinator and the Executive Committee ensure the overall alignment between project management and accountability. The Executive Committee provides the operational input for informed decision-making, while the Coordinator formalises it through official interactions with the European Commission.

The **WP Leaders Meeting (WPLM)** ensures coordination, coherence, and alignment across all WPs. It is pre-scheduled on a monthly basis, and addresses collaboratively a range of managerial and operational aspects related to:

- The implementation of the respective WPs in line with agreed objectives;
- Monitoring progress, identifying risks, and proposing mitigation strategies;
- Ensuring integration and consistency of outputs across WPs;
- Implementing decisions adopted by the General Assembly;

The **Services and Technology Board (STB)** brings together the Beneficiaries and Associated Partners responsible for the sustainability and further development of the EDCH platforms. It convenes monthly, and aims to provide support on technical procedures and standards of the project. More specifically, it contributes to:

- Assessing and guiding service development and integration;
- Ensuring interoperability across platforms and components;
- Monitoring technological risks and proposing mitigation measures;

- Supporting the adoption and effective use of project services

2.2.2 Internal communication and monitoring

Project shared space

A document repository has been set up on Google Drive, and is used to store and collaboratively edit non-confidential documents. Procedures for managing confidential materials are outlined in the DMP.

Participants are granted access to the shared drive using an email linked to a Google account. By default, new members are assigned the 'contributor' role, allowing them to upload, modify, move, or delete files. Folder and user management privileges are reserved for the coordinators, who can adjust access permissions.

The drive is structured into several main folders: six are assigned to the WPs, while others contain presentations, templates, deliverables, and documents from the project preparation phase. Each WP leader oversees their respective folder, and coordinators may create additional subfolders for tasks, deliverables, or other relevant materials.

Mailing lists

Internal communication within the project is primarily conducted via email. To ensure efficiency, all partners have shared the contact details of their respective team members, with a clear indication of their involvement in specific WPs and tasks. This information has been compiled into a shared spreadsheet accessible to the consortium.

In addition, a set of mailing lists has been established to facilitate coordination among relevant contributors:

- Dedicated mailing lists for each WP;
- A mailing list for the WP Leaders ;
- A mailing list for financial and administrative matters, supporting communication with legal signatories, human resources, and accounting personnel;

- A mailing list with designated representatives from beneficiaries and associated partners to coordinate outreach activities across the project;
- A mailing list for partners' representatives in the General Assembly

In addition to the mailing lists, dedicated channels on the Mattermost instance maintained by the Coordinator will be created upon request to facilitate immediate communication within the Consortium.

Meetings

Virtual meetings are organized on a regular basis to support the implementation of the project. Calendar invitations have been shared to maintain a consistent day and time slot for meetings to facilitate planning and participation. The coordinators or the respective WP leaders circulate the meeting agenda in advance. All participants confirm their attendance in the rolling minutes document and contribute to note-taking.

At the governance level, the frequency and organisation of meetings for each body are defined in the Consortium, which also specifies the notice period and deadlines for submitting agenda items.

Operational meetings, including those of WPs and specific tasks, follow a similar structure. Each WP is required to meet at least once per month under the coordination of the WP Leader, who may increase the frequency if necessary.

2.2.3 Reporting

There is one reporting period covering 24 project months. To ensure that resource consumption remains on track and aligned with activity performance, three intermediate reporting checkpoints have been established:

- Intermediate Reporting 1 covers M1-M9 (March 2026 ~ November 2026)
- Intermediate Reporting 2 covers M10-M18 (December 2026 ~ August 2027)
- Intermediate Reporting 3 covers M18-M24 (September 2027 ~ February 2028)

Reporting Period (M1-M24)

Image 3. Reporting periods

The project's internal financial management tool is EUFIN, a customised platform designed to support efficient and transparent financial monitoring. EUFIN systematically collects and consolidates financial data from each beneficiary, facilitates budget tracking against planned allocations, supports the verification of eligible costs, and enables early identification of deviations. Reporting steps are as follows:

#	Who	When	What	Details / Rules
1	Project Manager	Reporting due month (M)	Launch the intermediate reporting	
2	Beneficiary	M+20 days	Submit the report into the financial management tool EUfin	The report includes: -actual PM used -actual costs incurred
3	WP Leaders	M+ 30 days	Assess the status of PM and resources used in line with the project activities performed	
4	Board	During Board meeting	Review the use of resources	The review output will be used as the input to the section 5.2 of the Technical Report
For the periodic reporting, the steps continue:				
5	Beneficiary	M+ 45 days	Submit the financial statement in to the EC portal	The figures declared in the financial statement should be consistent with the resource use review approved by the board

6	Project Manager	M+ 55 days	Quality check	
7	Project Manager	M+ 60 days	Submit the periodic report	

Table 1. Reporting process

During the intermediate checks, partners examine the level of resources used against the original planning defined in the DoA. These additional checkpoints enable partners to regularly assess performance progress and evaluate whether any adjustments are needed to realise project's activities and objectives.

2.3 Project deliverables and milestones

A total of **15** deliverables and **21** milestones will be delivered in accordance with the project implementation timeframe detailed in the Grant Agreement. To ensure timely submission and high-quality results, the following procedures, responsibilities, and assignments apply to all deliverables and to milestones verified by a formal report:

1. Preparation

The preparation phase focuses on content creation. The WP leader facilitates this stage by coordinating with the lead author and co-authors to ensure that the draft of each deliverable is completed within the designated timeframe.

Assignments and Responsibilities: The lead author is responsible for ensuring the quality and relevance of the content. The WP leader oversees the process and monitors progress against the agreed deadlines.

Procedure: The lead author is responsible for drafting the deliverable, including collecting input from relevant tasks. Overall progress is reported by the lead author in WP meetings and by the WP leader in WPL meetings. Mitigation measures are agreed upon in case of deviations from the original preparation plan or the scope of the deliverable, or if changes in structure and content are required.

2. Review

The review is conducted to ensure that the deliverable is compliant with the project objectives and the requirements outlined in the Grant Agreement. Documents are evaluated based on their internal consistency and relevance of content.

Assignments and Responsibilities: The WP leader appoints the reviewers and oversees the timely review and revision of the document. The lead author is responsible for integrating the reviewers' comments and updating the document accordingly.

Procedure: To maintain an unbiased perspective, the WP leader appoints at least two reviewers who have not contributed to the deliverable. The lead author addresses the reviewers' comments, and any substantial suggested changes are discussed in WP meetings. The WP leader, unless acting as the lead author, approves the final draft version of the deliverable and/or milestone. The review process shall not exceed four weeks and must be completed at least 10 days prior to the deliverable's due date.

3. Quality control and submission

This final phase involves the validation of the document prior to its submission to the European Commission.

Assignments and Responsibilities: The project manager and the Principal Investigators verify that all required topics are covered, that the status of the work aligns with the project plan, and that the deliverable adheres to the designated stylistic guidelines and templates. The project manager also provides the necessary administrative support throughout this phase.

Procedure: A final review is conducted one week prior to the submission deadline. Technical details (e.g. consistent font usage, inclusion of acronyms, and completeness of the document history) are reviewed by the authors and the Executive Committee. The process concludes with the upload of the final PDF to the EC submission portal as part of the continuous reporting process. The editable ("open") version and the final PDF are stored in the project's document repository using an appropriate naming convention (AEGIS-OA_D[id]_[version]). The document is then uploaded to Zenodo.

Throughout the deliverable preparation process, the overall quality of the deliverable is verified against a list of predefined criteria (see Annex 2)

3. Risk Management

In the context of the project's implementation, a risk is considered as a condition or event that may negatively affect the project's progress, outputs, or overall impact. An initial set of potential risks and corresponding mitigation measures has been identified in the DoA. These risks will be continuously assessed during the meetings of the Executive Committee and within the WPLM, as part of the WP reporting procedure.

3.1 Risk Mitigation Plan

The identified risks have been recorded in the Risk Mitigation Plan (RMP), which establishes a systematic approach to identifying, assessing, managing, and monitoring risks and will thus serve as a reference tool for ongoing monitoring activities. The current list of entries, as presented in the Annex, will be complemented with any additional risks that will emerge during the project's timeline.

The RMP defines the governance and monitoring mechanisms in place and applies a structured assessment methodology, evaluating each risk in terms of its likelihood and potential impact. The plan further outlines risk response strategies that include mitigation actions and contingency planning. This approach enables effective prioritisation, ensures that focus and resources are directed toward the most significant risks, and outlines predefined responses that can be implemented efficiently when required.

3.2 Continuous Risk Assessment

Additionally, the plan incorporates reviewing procedures to continuously track risks, enhance the effectiveness of response measures, and maintain the accuracy and relevance of the RMP (see Annex). All identified risks will be reviewed at regular intervals in collaboration with the WP Leaders, to ensure that:

- New risks are identified in a timely manner;
- Existing risks are re-assessed based on updated information;
- Mitigation measures remain effective;
- 'Closed' risks are formally documented

Prior to each internal review, relevant data –such as progress on mitigation actions and any new developments affecting risk exposure– will be collected from the respective WPs. Each risk will be then reassessed in terms of likelihood and impact. Changes in context will be reflected in the risk's updated rating and prioritisation, while existing mitigation measures will be evaluated for effectiveness in accordance with the following framework:

- **Mitigation measures are sufficient:** the controls and actions already in place effectively reduce the risk to an acceptable level. The risk is considered well-managed, requiring only monitoring
- **Mitigation measures are partially sufficient:** steps have been taken to address the risk, but the current measures do not adequately reduce it. There is a need for refinement
- **Further treatment is required:** current mitigation measures are either absent or inadequate. The risk demands immediate attention, and the development and implementation of new controls or interventions to effectively manage.

These categories facilitate an evolving assessment of risks. This process also provides an opportunity to identify new risks that may have emerged since the previous review. Where necessary, mitigation actions will be adjusted or replaced to better address both existing and recently identified risks. All updates will be recorded in the RMP, and reviewed with relevant WP leaders to ensure alignment. Any new or revised actions resulting from the assessment will be systematically tracked through to completion.

4. Conclusion

The Quality and Risk Management Plan serves as a central reference framework for the overall coordination and management of the project. It provides structured guidance to systematically monitor progress, assess the quality of activities and outputs, and proactively evaluate and mitigate potential risks that may emerge throughout the project lifecycle.

The plan also promotes transparency, accountability, and alignment with the project's objectives and standards. Its dissemination within the consortium fosters a coordinated and efficient approach to implementation, ensuring that all partners are supported to respond effectively to challenges and potential deviations from the workplan.

Annex 1 : Risk Mitigation Plan

Risks identified in the proposal and during the Grant Agreement preparation

Risk No	1	2	3	4	5	6
Identification	Proposal	Proposal	Proposal	Proposal	Proposal	GA preparation
WP	WP1	WP1	All	WP5	All	All
Risk description	A partner leaves the consortium	Branding confusion between the EDCH and the Project	Delays in reporting, deliverables, or WP activities	Lack of adoption of project outputs	Insufficient budget to complete the project objectives	Single reporting period (M1-M24)
Risk monitored by	Executive Committee; Coordinator	Executive Committee; WPL	Executive Committee; Coordinator	Executive Committee; WPL	Executive Committee; WPL	Executive Committee; Coordinator
Monitoring process	Official communication between the partner, the Coordinator, and the EC	Risk review and evaluation during WPL meeting	Risk review and evaluation during WPL meeting	Risk review and evaluation during WPL meeting	Risk review and evaluation during WPL meeting	Regular reviews of reported effort and costs
Probability	Low	Low	Medium	Medium	High	Medium
Severity	High	Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium
Impact	1) Tasks and budget must be redistributed among existing or new beneficiaries 2) Trigger risk #3	1) Confusion: stakeholders and users may not distinguish the project's contributions from EDCH activities 2) Trigger risk #4	1) Potentially trigger risk #4 2) Diversions from implementation timeplan 3) Potentially trigger risk #5	1) KPIs are not achieved 2) Outputs fail to reach or benefit the intended target groups 3) Outputs are not maintained or used beyond the project lifetime	1) KPIs are not achieved 2) Planned activities or outputs scaled back	1) Partners over- or underspend 2) Ongoing and planned activities scaled back
Mitigation measures	Procedures for replacing a partner or redistribution of tasks described in the Consortium Agreement	Communication strategy to be outlined in the Project's Dissemination, Outreach, and Exploitation Plan	Regular meetings involving the Executive Committee and partners responsible	1) Target stakeholders via the NCC network. 2) NCC Board to recommend outreach and dissemination activities	The project funding is complemented by in-kind contributions in the framework of the EDCH	Intermediate reporting checkpoints in M9 and M18

Continuous risk assessment

Risk #	1	2	3	4	5	6
Risk Description	A partner leaves the consortium	Branding confusion between the EDCH and the Project	Delays in reporting, deliverables, or WP activities	Lack of adoption of project outputs	Insufficient budget to complete the project objectives	Single reporting period (M1-M24)
Work Package No(s)	WP1	WP1	All	WP5	All	
Review # (Month)						
Result of the risk assessment						
Identified threat(s) during risk review						
Updated Mitigation Plan						
Next risk review date						

Annex 2: Deliverable Quality Checklist

This checklist ensures that all project deliverables meet agreed quality standards before submission. It is used throughout the lifecycle of a deliverable by: authors (preparation of the final deliverable); reviewers (quality assessment); the Executive Committee (pre-submission control and final validation)

1. Scope and relevance (authors; reviewers)

- Objectives are clearly addressed and consistent with the Description of Action
- The deliverable reflects planned activities and outputs, and content is relevant to the WP objectives
- Alignment with related deliverables is ensured
- All planned contributions from partners are integrated
- Information is accurate, up to date, and evidence-based
- Appropriate level of detail regarding the applied methodology, processes, and outputs is provided
- Used terms are consistent with the project terminology

2. Completeness and Format (authors; reviewers)

- Project official template is used, and style guides are followed
- All mandatory sections are included and completed
- Figures, tables, and annexes are included and referenced
- All referenced materials are properly listed and accessible
- Document follows required formatting and naming conventions

3. Quality Assurance (authors; executive committee)

- Reviewer comments are documented and addressed
- Deliverable complies with legal and ethical requirements; data protection, licensing, and Open Science requirements considered – where applicable
- History of changes is clear and traceable; final version is updated correctly before submission
- File format, naming, and submission requirements verified
- Final approval from respective WP leader received